
LETTER FROM THE EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Dear Readers and Authors!

This is the first issue of the new scientific digital journal "Population and Economics".

Continuing the traditions of Professor Dmitry Ignatievich Valentey's university demographic school, we have planned to make an interdisciplinary journal devoted to the discussion of issues related to population. The subject area of the research, the results of which we plan to present on the pages of the journal, covers the research interests of disciplines such as demography, population economics, labor economics, social policy, behavioral economics, institutional economics, macroeconomics, marketing research, socio-economic geography, economic sociology and other disciplines. It seems that it is at interdisciplinary crossroads of different sciences that the discoveries in the coming decades will be made.

The Journal welcomes the use of various research methods – methods of demographic analysis and forecasting, econometric and other mathematical methods, quantitative and qualitative sociological methods, as well as ones from other sciences. An interdisciplinary approach involves the mutual usage of methods from different sciences.

An important feature of the modern scientific reality is an unprecedented increase in the volume of information and data on population. This broadens the possibilities of analysis and simultaneously requires the creation of a culture of data exchange. I mean data formed by the authors for the research purpose, to continue dialogue on the issue raised and to involve young researchers in this dialogue. Therefore, we encourage authors to place their working databases and author codes in open access on the pages of our journal.

The journal opens various sections. Apart original articles, we will publish a methodical section for teachers "The Teacher's Podium". And "Demographic calendar" on the most important events and people in the world of population sciences. In the "Reviews" section we plan to present the most discussed scientific works. There will be a "Discussions" section on the pages of which we invite scientists to argue about unresolved theoretical issues and new methods, and other sections.

The first issue of the magazine offers to your attention, dear readers, theoretical and empirical research on relevant subjects, performed by authors with the usage of various methods. The "Teacher's Podium" and "Demographic calendar" are open.

We invite researchers from different regions of Russia and other countries to argue, publish their scientific results, share created databases, methods of teaching sciences on the population.

We invite readers interested in the issues raised on the pages of our journal to attentive reading and cooperation with editors and authors.

I would like to wish all of us a valuable journal and the pleasure of creating and reading the materials in the journal's section "Population and Economics".

Irina E. Kalabikhina

Moscow, MSU, December 2017